

Co-funded by the European Union

Digital Educational Network For Cultural
Projects Implementation And Direction

About the Project:

DEN-CuPID is a Strategic Partnership (SP) between SMEs, academic institutions and local authorities associations, which aims primarily at improving transversal competencies, such as entrepreneurship and managerial skills, and at enhancing knowledge in the field of cultural management. It envisages the optimization of local capacities in designing and implementing projects based on the local cultural endowment, as well as the ability to involve financial and innovative funding tools, for the accomplishment of these projects.

Partners involved:

The project has a duration of two years and is run under the auspices of the State Scholarships Foundation (IKY), the Hellenic National Agency of the Erasmus+ programme.

The participant countries and the partners involved in the SP are the following:

- Greece (E- Trikala S.A. Hellenic National Commission for UNESCO, Time Heritage LTD, Department of Cultural Heritage Management and New Technologies (University of Patra) and E.G.T.C. Amphictyony)
- Italy (Associazione di Promozione Sociale Futuro Digitale)
- Spain (VEA QUALITAS, S.L)
- Bulgaria (UNION OF BULGARIAN BLACK SEA LOCAL AUTHORITIES SDRUZHENIE).
UBBSLA

Kick off meeting:

The projects kick off meeting took place in Trikala (GREECE) on the 24th and the 25th of November 2016. All partners took part in this crucial meeting that mainly worked with topics such as: establishing the case studies for each region (Greece, Italy, Spain and Bulgaria), setting up a time schedule for each workshop to take place and dealing with all the important managerial issues.

Each partner will create a 4 days' workshop that deals with good practices in relation to tourism, heritage and cultural management. All 4 case studies in relation to these workshops are defined and currently under refinement:

Greece: *"Creating the largest Christmas Park in Greece, from theory to practice"*

Case Study abstract: The Mill of Elves is the largest and most successful Christmas event in Greece over the last six years.

It has won the smiles, admiration and positive feedback from hundreds of thousands of visitors from every corner of the country and has featured in all major television networks and more generally in the media with hundreds of specials, reports and interviews. The "Mill of Elves" can serve as an example of organizing a theme park and thus enhancing municipal historic infrastructure.

Spain:

Case study abstract: A must for all tourists that arrive in Zaragoza is to visit the Aljaferia Palace, which is the second most visited historic site in Zaragoza.

The importance of Aljaferia lies in the fact that it is the only preserved building from the Hispanic Islamic architecture of the Taifas time. The mudejar remains of the Palace of Aljaferia were declared a World Heritage Site by Unesco in 2001 as a part of the whole "Mudéjar Architecture of Aragon". The Palace of Aljaferia belongs to the Parliament of the Regional Government (Aragon Government) and the Parliament sessions are held there. This is a very important fact that assures the sustainability of the building and its preservation and it is also a good example of the juggle of public, cultural and touristic usages and of the impact on private enterprises.

The location of the Aljaferia in the city has a very important and positive impact on the private and local business around it, because of the amount of visitants and public employees.

Bulgaria:

Case study abstract: The present case study represents the cultural and historic identity of Varna, Bulgaria as the biggest city in the Black Sea coasts which hosts thousands of tourists annually. The main objective is to provide sufficient information of culture heritage in the city development for the training needs of municipals, experts and specialists in tourism, guides, tourist operators and those working in tourism. It is a tourist route encompassing several trail stops in the center of Varna, which can be reached and visited by walking and to be acquainted with the historic development of the city. Some of the main culture heritage monuments are to be promoted in a way highlighting the social and emotional sense and historic interpretation. Varna is a touristic city visited by thousands of people who are getting known with the main attractions, significant buildings and monuments especially in the city centre where the majority of assets are concentrated. This is the reason the tenth objects to be identified and presented within the concept of the economic and industrial revival of Varna as a commercial and maritime city.

Italy:

Case study abstract: The objective of this study is to scrutinise and show the potential/drawbacks of digital storytelling as a means of developing a marketing dimension of Latina County (central Italy), suffering the overwhelming role of Rome as huge touristic hub. For the purposes of Erasmus plus Den-Cupid project, #Outofrome work sheds light on the way digital storytelling can be used and practiced and how cooperation among stakeholders is a complementary part of using storytelling as destination development strategy. The study aims to:

- Produce a specific analysis on Latina county and its specific storytelling destination situation and possible development based on qualitative research methods;
- Use a theoretical model defined as an integration between storytelling, network and policy theory;
- Give specific views on storytelling and stakeholder cooperation;
- Understand from the learning-by-doing process of Den-Cupid which are the SWOT points of the adopted approach;
- Work in close cooperation with detected stakeholder along the Den-Cupid development process and disseminate the results from the storytelling study

Objectives:

The SP will design and develop high quality and innovative tools and training courses for training and coaching municipalities' employees and local actors involved or interested in cultural management projects and ventures. In this way, we aim to:

- Support local actors in fostering the idea and practice of cultural management as a tool for sustainable development, through familiarizing themselves with local history, local heritage assets, raising public awareness in heritage issues,
- Encourage partnership and collaborative development processes between the local authorities and the local communities' members, and bringing them together with research and educational institutions in order foster cluster-generating capabilities,
- Enable aspiring cultural entrepreneurs and municipalities employees to familiarize themselves with various forms of financial instruments and other funding opportunities, as well as methodologies for effective management
- Stimulate the development of their entrepreneurial, creative and innovation skills, and their capacity to turn ideas and concepts about local cultural assets into original projects and sustainable business plans,
- Providing the possibility of international networking and exchange of experience,
- Encourage sharing of crowd-wisdom and employing crowd-sourcing.

An important aspect of the project will be the overall assessment of needs in the field of cultural (and cultural heritage) management across Europe as well as the investigation of the steps to be taken to remedy discrepancies and problems on various levels, including technical knowledge, managerial skills, lateral thinking, modular design of projects and finally even legislative measures.

Project Site:

In order to disseminate the Den_CuPIDs idea and objectives as well as communicate all the intellectual input that will derive from this effort a site has been created:

<http://den-cupid.eu>

Comparative International Survey

An online survey has been designed and carried out with the aim to assess the situation regarding local cultural assets and practices, and record the needs and attitudes of those involved in cultural/heritage projects, such as local authorities, NGOs, cultural societies, private institutions and local businesses.

The intention is to use the results so as to design and develop high quality and innovative tools and training courses for training and coaching municipalities' employees and local actors involved or interested in cultural management projects and ventures.

The initial questionnaire was drafted in English. Greek, Bulgarian, Spanish and Italian versions of the questionnaire were produced with the help of the partners. The survey was set up with survey monkey and will be open for a period of two months.

The leading organisation of this intellectual output is the Department of Cultural Heritage Management and New Technologies (University of Patras) and participating organisations are: Time Heritage, Hellenic National Commission for UNESCO, Veia Qualitas, S.L. Associazione di Promozione Sociale Futuro Digitale, UNION OF BULGARIAN BLACK SEA LOCALAUTHORITIES SDRUZHENIE, ANAPTYXIAKI ETAIREIA DIMOU TRIKKAION ANAPTYXIAKI ANONYMI ETAIREIA OTA – E-TRIKALA.

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